

Supplementary Information.

Shining bright at 960 nm: a 28-silver-atom nanorod stabilized by DNA

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Materials and Methods

1. Synthesis of DNA960-AgNC

The oligonucleotide (5'-CCGCGCGCGCCGCGAA-3') and nuclease-free water were purchased from Integrated DNA Technologies (IDT). AgNO₃ (≥ 99.998%), NaBH₄ (≥ 99.99%) and ammonium acetate (NH₄OAc, ≥98%) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. All chemicals were used as received and dissolved in nuclease-free H₂O. DNA-AgNCs were synthesized by mixing a hydrated DNA solution with AgNO₃ in a 10 mM or 50 mM NH₄OAc solution (pH=7). After 15 minutes, a fresh solution of NaBH₄ was added. The concentrations of the components in the final mixture were 30 μM for the DNA, 240 μM AgNO₃ and 240 μM NaBH₄. Both 10 mM and 50 mM NH₄OAc were found to favor the same DNA-AgNC, with a better yield of formation in case of 50 mM. The solution was stored in the fridge for 5 days before HPLC purification. Figure S1 shows the absorption spectrum of the as-synthesized solution before HPLC purification.

Regarding the origin of the chlorides, we note that the certificate of analysis of ammonium acetate mentions an amount of Cl⁻ ≤ 5 ppm. The IDT nuclease-free water is certified up to a conductivity of ≤ 2 μS/cm, indicating that non-negligible amounts of ions (and chloride) could be present in the water.

2. HPLC purification

The HPLC purification was performed with an Agilent Technologies 1260 Infinity fluorescence detector, an Agilent Technologies 1100 Series UV-Vis detector, a C18 column (Phenomenex) and a fraction collector. The mobile phase was gradually changed and made of a mixture of 35 mM triethylammonium acetate (TEAA) buffer in water (solvent A) and 35 mM TEAA in methanol (solvent B). The gradient was as follows:

Time	% B
0 min	5
2 min	5
27 min	30
30 min	95

The separation run was followed by 5 minutes at 95% B to remove any remaining sample from the column. Figure S2 shows the chromatograms of the 960-nm emissive DNA-AgNC. The retention time with the abovementioned method is between 23 and 24 minutes. The DNA-AgNC sample was purified twice with the same HPLC method to improve the purity. The first run was performed using a LUNA C18 column (5 μm, 100 Å, 250 x 10 mm, Phenomenex) with a flow rate of 4.7 mL/min, while the second run was carried out with a Kinetex C18 column (5 μm, 100 Å, 250 x 4.6 mm, Phenomenex) with a flow rate of 1 mL/min. Afterwards, the purified DNA-AgNC solution was solvent-exchanged to either 10 mM or 50 mM NH₄OAc with 3 kDa cut-off membrane filters (Amicon Ultra), depending on which NH₄OAc solution was used to synthesize the clusters. Figure S3 shows the absorption spectra after the first and second purification.

Figure S1. Absorption spectrum of the as-synthesized DNA₂-[Ag₂₈]¹⁶⁺ in 50 mM NH₄OAc, 5 days after synthesis. Given the absorbance of 0.045 at 835 nm and a molar absorption coefficient of 210000 M⁻¹·cm⁻¹, the DNA-AgNC concentration can be estimated to be 2.14·10⁻⁷ M.

Figure S2. HPLC chromatograms of DNA₂-[Ag₂₈]¹⁶⁺, monitoring the absorbance at **A)** 830 nm and **B)** 260 nm. The absorbance is given in mOD. **C)** Chromatograms that monitor the emission at 900 nm, exciting at 830 nm. The dashed red lines define the collected fraction.

Figure S3. Normalized absorption spectra of DNA₂-[Ag₂₈]¹⁶⁺ in 50 mM NH₄OAc purified once (purple) and twice (pink) by HPLC.

3. Spectroscopic measurements

3.1 Steady-state absorption measurements

Absorption spectra were measured with a LAMBDA 1050 UV/Vis/NIR spectrophotometer from Perkin Elmer using a deuterium lamp for ultraviolet radiation and a tungsten-halogen lamp for visible and near-infrared (NIR) radiation. All measurements were performed in a single-beam configuration with a “zero/baseline” correction, *i.e.*, measuring the 100%/0% transmittance with air as reference. The corresponding solvent spectra were measured separately and then subtracted from the samples’ spectra. The absorbance of the samples was kept below 0.1 to avoid inner filter effects during emission measurements.

3.2 Fluorescence spectra and decay time measurements on a home-built microscope

Emission spectra and decay time measurements were performed on our home-built confocal microscope.¹ A continuum white-light laser (SuperK EXTREME EXB-6, NKT Photonics) was used as an excitation source delivering a wavelength of 790 nm by sending the continuum output through an acousto-optic tunable filter (SuperK SELECT, NKT Photonics). The output of the laser was expanded and collimated by a lens system and cleaned up by an 800 nm short-pass filter (FESH0800, Thorlabs) before it was reflected by a 30:70 beam splitter (XF122, Omega Optical) and sent through an objective. For the spectrum and decay shown in Figure 1A, an oil immersion objective (UPlanSApo 100x, NA = 1.4, Olympus) was used, while for the quantum yield (Figure S4) an air objective (CPlanFLN 10x, NA= 0.3, Olympus) was utilized. The objective that collected the fluorescence was directed through a 100 μm pinhole and an 815 nm long-pass filter (HQ815LP, Chroma). For the recording of the spectra, the fluorescence was then sent through a spectrograph (SP 2356 spectrometer, 300 grooves/mm, Acton Research) onto a nitrogen-cooled CCD camera (SPEC-10:100B/LN-eXcelon, Princeton Instruments). The emission spectra were wavelength- and intensity-corrected as reported previously.¹ For

measuring the fluorescence decays, a flip mirror was used to direct the emission towards an avalanche photodiode (CD3226, PerkinElmer) connected to a single photon counting board (SPC-830, Becker & Hickl).

For the quantum yield measurements, standard 1 cm quartz cuvettes (Hellma) were filled with either the blank (10 mM NH₄OAc; used for subtracting residual laser scatter), a solution of the 960-nm emissive DNA-AgNC, or a solution of the reference (see section 3.3). The cuvettes were placed on top of the microscope's sample stage, and the laser was focused around 1 mm into the solutions ensuring that the spectra were recorded under identical conditions. Furthermore, the spectra were measured with 780 nm excitation accompanied by a change of the excitation filter (LL01-780-25, Semrock) and emission filter (LP02-785RU-25, Semrock).

The fluorescence decays were fitted with FluoFit 4.6 software (PicoQuant) using a 2- or 3-exponential reconvolution model including the instrument response function (IRF) to obtain a good fit. The intensity-weighted average lifetime, $\langle\tau\rangle$, of the DNA-AgNC in solution was found to be 0.65 ns. Table S1 contains all amplitude and decay time components as well as the reduced χ^2 of the fit, while the decay curve, IRF and corresponding fit are reported in Figure 1B. The intensity-weighted average lifetimes of the DNA-AgNC crystals are instead provided in the caption of Figure S5.

Table S1. Amplitude and lifetime components, together with reduced χ^2 , obtained from the fit of the fluorescence decay curve of the 960-nm emitting DNA-AgNC measured in 10 mM NH₄OAc at room temperature ($\lambda_{exc}=790$ nm).

A ₁	1606.4
τ_1	1.1065
A ₂	26156
τ_2	0.70570
A ₃	104170
τ_3	0.027262
χ^2 (red.)	1.051

3.3 Quantum yield determination

The quantum yield of DNA₂-[Ag₂₈]¹⁶⁺ was determined in 10 mM NH₄OAc aqueous solution at room temperature, using DNA750-AgNC in the same medium as reference ($QY_{ref} = 0.46$).² Absorption and emission spectra were measured at one concentration for both DNA₂-[Ag₂₈]¹⁶⁺ and reference. The blue-edge of the emission spectrum of the reference was corrected by combining the spectrum recorded on the microscope (section 3.2) with the spectrum measured with a FluoTime300 instrument (PicoQuant) exciting at 726 nm (LDH-P-C-730). The quantum yield was then calculated to be 0.12 according to equation 1:³

$$QY = \frac{F_{DNA-AgNC}}{f_{A,DNA-AgNC}} \cdot \frac{f_{A,ref}}{F_{ref}} \cdot \frac{n_{DNA-AgNC}^2}{n_{ref}^2} \cdot QY_{ref} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Where QY represents the quantum yield of DNA₂-[Ag₂₈]¹⁶⁺, F is the integrated emission spectrum (*i.e.*, the area under the fluorescence spectrum), f_A defines the fraction of absorbed light at the excitation wavelength (780 nm), and n is the refractive index of the medium where the compounds are dissolved. The subscripts *DNA-AgNC* and *ref* indicate the DNA-AgNC investigated in this study and DNA750-AgNC, respectively.

The absorption and emission spectra of both DNA-AgNCs are reported in Figure S4.

Figure S4. Quantum yield data. **A)** Absorption and **B)** emission spectra of DNA₂-[Ag₂₈]¹⁶⁺ (sample) and DNA750-AgNC (reference) measured in 10 mM NH₄OAc at room temperature. The emission spectra were recorded exciting at 780 nm.

3.4 Fluorescence spectra and decay time measurements of crystals on superconducting nanowire single photon detector setup

To properly measure the spectral features and decay times of DNA₂-[Ag₂₈Cl₂]¹⁴⁺ crystals within the NIR II region, we utilized our superconducting nanowire single photon detector (SNSPD) setup, which was based on a microscope (IX73, Olympus) configuration (see Figure S5). For excitation, we used the output from a fiber coupled (FD7-PM, NKT Photonics) 13 MHz pulsed continuum white-light laser (SuperK EXTREME EXB-6, NKT Photonics) simultaneously delivering a set of wavelengths of 820 nm, 830 nm, and 840 nm by sending the continuum output through an acousto-optic tunable filter (AOTF; SuperK SELECT, NKT Photonics). The output of the fiber was expanded (BE05M-A, Thorlabs) and cleaned up by a single short-pass filter (FESH0900, Thorlabs). The excitation light was directed towards the microscope and was reflected by a 30:70 beam splitter (XF122, Omega Optical) and sent through an oil immersion objective (UPlanSApo 100x, NA = 1.4, Olympus). The objective focused the laser onto the sample and collected the luminescence. To block laser bleed-through, a long-pass filter was inserted in the detection path (FELH0900, Thorlabs). Because of the polarization sensitivity of the detector, we added a polarizing beam splitter (PBS102, Thorlabs) in the path (this is mainly for intensity calibration purposes where light from an unpolarized lamp is used).

The resulting emission was directed through a monochromator (SpectraPro 2300i, Princeton Instruments) and expanded (GBE05-C, Thorlabs). The emission was then directed towards an objective (Plan N, 40x, NA = 0.65, Olympus) positioned on a fiber launch system (MBT613D/M, Thorlabs) for coupling into a single mode fiber (ENI/1092976, Diamond). The fiber was then coupled into a cryogenic SNSPD system (ID281, IDQ). The single photon detection events were directed to a delay generator (DG535, Stanford Research) to ensure that TTL pulses were fed to a single photon counting board (SPC-830, Becker & Hickl).

All SNSPD data was collected using LabVIEW. Official VIs from Becker & Hickl and Princeton Instruments were modified and combined and allowed for collecting time

resolved emission maps;⁴ here, we only show the integrated decays or spectra. Wavelength and intensity calibrations were performed as previously described.¹ For calibrating the wavelength, we used selected wavelength outputs from our supercontinuum laser. Because of the SNSPD's large spectral range and the limited wavelength availability of our AOTF (690 – 1100 nm), we also used the second harmonics for calibration purposes. The intensity was calibrated using a calibration lamp (SL1-CAL, StellarNet Inc).

Figure S5. **A)** Emission spectra and **B)** fluorescence decay curves of the DNA₂-[Ag₂₈Cl₂]¹⁴⁺ crystals, exciting at 790 nm. The gray curve in **B** is the instrument response function. The intensity-weighted lifetimes of the five measured crystals range from 0.16 to 0.23 ns.

Figure S6. Comparison of the emission spectra of DNA₂-[Ag₂₈]¹⁶⁺ in 50 mM NH₄OAc in solution (droplet on top of a glass coverslip, light green); when dried (dark blue) and from a crystal of DNA₂-[Ag₂₈Cl₂]¹⁴⁺ (dark green).

3.5 Molar absorption coefficient (ϵ) determination

The molar absorption coefficient of the 960-nm emissive DNA-AgNC was determined as reported by Romolini *et al.* employing inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES).² For this purpose, the sample was purified twice *via* HPLC using the same method described above. The ICP-OES calibration curves for silver are reported in Figure S7 together with the absorption spectrum of the DNA-AgNC.

The ϵ value at 835 nm was found to be $210000 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Figure S7. ICP-OES calibration curves for DNA₂-[Ag₂₈]¹⁶⁺ using different emission lines of Ag: **A)** 243.8 nm, **B)** 328 nm, and **C)** 338 nm. The blue dot indicates the amount of Ag in the sample. **D)** Absorption spectrum of the sample measured in 50 mM NH₄OAc at room temperature.

Table S2. Comparison with FDA-approved NIR fluorophores.

	λ_{abs} [nm]	λ_{em} [nm]	Quantum yield (ϕ)	Absorption coefficient (ϵ) [M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹]	Brightness ($\phi \cdot \epsilon$) [M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹]

Indocyanine Green	779	805	0.029	156000	4524
Methylene Blue	664	688	0.22	67000	14740
DNA ₂ -[Ag ₂₈] ¹⁶⁺	835	960	0.12	210000	25200

Indocyanine Green data was taken from Cosco *et al.*⁵ Methylene Blue data was taken from Shahinyan *et al.* and Ghanadzadeh *et al.*^{6, 7} Note that both Indocyanine Green and Methylene Blue have a tendency to aggregate in water and hence the fluorescence response can be very concentration-dependent.

3.6 Fluorescence excitation anisotropy

The steady-state excitation anisotropy of DNA₂-[Ag₂₈]¹⁶⁺ was measured in 99% glycerol and 1% 50 mM NH₄OAc at 10 °C using a QuantaMaster 400 instrument from PTI. To measure the four orientations, two polarizers (LPNIRE100-B, Thorlabs) were added, one in the excitation path and the other one in the emission path. Additionally, a 633 nm longpass filter (BLP01-633R-25, Semrock) was placed in the excitation path to block higher order reflections. Parallel (I_{VV} , I_{HH}) and perpendicular (I_{VH} , I_{HV}) excitation spectra were recorded, monitoring the emission at 850 nm. These data were used to calculate the instrumental G factor ($G=I_{HV}/I_{HH}$) and the limiting anisotropy (r_0) of DNA₂-[Ag₂₈]¹⁶⁺ using equation 2:

$$r_0 = \frac{I_{VV} - G \cdot I_{VH}}{I_{VV} + 2G \cdot I_{VH}} \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

A r_0 value of 0.35 (close to the maximum value of 0.4) was found over the entire excitation band (see Figure S8).

Figure S8. A) Fluorescence excitation anisotropy (monitoring the emission at 850 nm) of DNA₂-[Ag₂₈]¹⁶⁺ in 99% glycerol and 1% 50 mM NH₄OAc at 10 °C. **B)** Excitation spectrum in the vertical-vertical polarization configuration.

4. Structure determination

4.1 Crystallization

Crystals were grown in an incubator at 293 K by the hanging drop vapor diffusion method. 0.2-1 μL of DNA-AgNC solution, with $[\text{DNA}] \approx 250 \mu\text{M}$, were mixed with 0.2-1 μL of crystallization buffer and equilibrated against 250 μL of a reservoir solution, either 40% 2-methyl-2,4-pentanediol (MPD) or 40% polyethylene glycol (PEG) 3350. The crystallization buffer contains either 10% MPD or 10% PEG 3350, a nitrate salt (Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , NH_4^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} or Sr^{2+}) with different concentrations (10, 100, 200, 300, 400 and 500 mM), 10 mM spermine and 50 mM 3-(N-morpholino)propanesulfonic acid (MOPS) at pH 7. Crystals were obtained with most conditions between 1 and 4 weeks after starting the crystallization. Examples are reported in Figure S9.

Figure S9. Examples of several crystals grown in 10% MPD, 10 mM spermine, 50 mM MOPS (pH 7) and 10 mM NaNO_3 (**A**, **C**), 10 mM $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (**B**), and 200 mM $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (**D**). The pictures in A and C were taken 5 months and 3 weeks after starting the crystallization, while those in B and D were taken approximately two months after the beginning of the crystallization.

4.2 Data collection, processing, phasing and refinement

To determine the structure of $\text{DNA}_2\text{-}[\text{Ag}_{28}\text{Cl}_2]^{14+}$, we collected datasets from two crystals. Data collection of the first crystal of $\text{DNA}_2\text{-}[\text{Ag}_{28}\text{Cl}_2]^{14+}$ was performed in BL-5A of Photon

Factory (Japan). The diffraction patterns were obtained with 1° oscillation steps with 0.2 s exposure time. A total of 720 frames were recorded by rotating the crystal. For the second crystal, the diffraction data was collected in bioMAX at MAX IV (Sweden). The diffraction patterns were obtained with 0.1° oscillation steps with 0.01 s exposure time. A total of 3600 frames were recorded. All datasets were processed with the program *XDS*.⁸ The reflection data were converted by *Reflection file editor* of the *Phenix suite*.⁹ The locations of 28 silvers were determined by the standard direct method phasing protocol in *SIR2019* using the diffraction data of the first crystal.¹⁰ The initial phase was instead estimated by employing the program *AutoSol* in the *Phenix suite*⁹ using the second diffraction data and the location of the 28 silvers as the reference heavy atom sites. The crystal structure was constructed by using the program *Coot*.^{11, 12} The atomic parameters were refined using the program *phenix.refine* in the *Phenix suite*.⁹ Crystal data, statistics of data collection, and structure refinement are summarized in Table S3.

Table S3. Crystal data, statistics of data collections, and structure refinement.

	Silver location determination	Overall modeling and refinement
<u>Crystal data</u>		
Space group	$P2_1$	$P2_1$
Unit cell (\AA , $^\circ$)	$a = 26.8$, $b = 53.2$, $c = 26.8$ $\beta = 103.3$	$a = 27.2$, $b = 53.2$, $c = 27.2$ $\beta = 103.7$
Z^a	1	1
<u>Data collection</u>		
Beamline	BL-5A of PF	bioMAX of MAX IV
Wavelength (\AA)	1.9	0.6199
Resolution (\AA)	26.6-2.0	16.8-1.3
of the outer shell (\AA)	2.1-2.0	1.34-1.30
Unique reflections	9242	35423
Completeness (%)	95.7	97.2
in the outer shell (%)	90.47	96.8
R_{anom}^b (%)	10.3	11.1
in the outer shell (%)	16.0	31.7
Redundancy	6.3	3.7
in the outer shell	5.3	3.6
<u>Phasing</u>		
	Direct method	SAD method
<u>Structure refinement</u>		
PDB ID		9KHW
Resolution range (\AA)		16.8-1.3
Used reflections		35398
R -factor ^c (%)		16.3
R_{free}^d (%)		16.4
Number of DNA atoms		646
Number of Ag		28
Number of Cl		2
Number of water		39
R.m.s.d. bond length (\AA)		0.009
R.m.s.d. bond angles ($^\circ$)		1.2

^a Number of DNA-silver nanocluster in the asymmetric unit.

^b $R_{\text{anom}} = 100 \times \sum_{hkl} |I_{hkl}(+) - I_{hkl}(-)| / \sum_{hkl} [I_{hkl}(+) + I_{hkl}(-)]$.

^c R -factor = $100 \times \sum (|F_o| - |F_c|) / \sum |F_o|$, where $|F_o|$ and $|F_c|$ are optimally scaled observed and calculated structure factor amplitudes, respectively.

^d Calculated using a random set containing 10% of observations.

Figure S10. Silver to silver, chlorine, nitrogen and oxygen bond distances, based on the PDB-ID 9KHW structure. For Ag-Ag, values up to 3.4 Å are reported, while for Ag-O, values up to 2.8 Å were taken into consideration.

Figure S11. Silver-mediated C₂-C₄-C₁₁-C₁₃ (A) and C₁-G₅-C₁₀-G₁₄ (B) quartets. Hydrogen bonds and silver-base interactions are shown as red and black dashed lines, respectively. The numbers indicate the distances in Å.

Figure S12. Two hydrogen bonds formed between the hydroxyl group at 5' of C₁ and the oxygen of the C₈ phosphate group contribute to the DNA-AgNC formation. Red dashed lines indicate the hydrogen bonds with the distances in Å.

Figure S13. Comparison of the electron density maps at the position of the chlorido ligands. The $2|F_o| - |F_c|$ map (blue) and $|F_o| - |F_c|$ map (green or red) are drawn at the contour level 1σ and 4σ , respectively. Two chlorides in the position Cl1 and Cl2 were replaced by other elements and water, and then the maps were calculated by *Phenix refine* of the Phenix suite.⁹

5. Electrospray ionization-Mass Spectrometry (ESI-MS)

ESI-MS measurements were performed on two samples: the 960-nm emissive DNA-AgNC solution and the same solution with NaCl ([DNA-AgNC]:[NaCl]=15 μ M:1.5 mM); the latter measured 5 minutes after the addition of the salt.

The ESI-MS data were acquired with a Xevo G2-XS QToF (Waters Corporation), using negative ion mode with a 1.5 kV capillary voltage, 30 V cone voltage, 80 V source offset and collision mode set to off. Spectra were collected from m/z 750 to 4000, with a scan time of 1 s. The source temperature was 100 °C with a cone gas flow of 50 L/h, and the desolvation temperature and gas flow were 350 °C and 800 L/h, respectively. The QTOF was calibrated using ESI-L Low Tune Mix (Agilent Technologies), which contained compounds for negative mode in the mass range of m/z 113 to 2834. The sample was injected using an Acquity I-Class Plus system (Waters) with a flow-through needle autosampler, with a flow of 0.05 mL/min 50 mM NH₄OAc at pH 7 MeOH (80:20) and using 3 μ L injection volume. The system was operated using UNIFI v.1.9.4 (Waters), and the final spectra were generated by averaging multiple spectra surrounding the apex of the observed peak. The recorded data were analyzed and fitted with the open-source software MSTools software developed by Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Lausanne.¹³

Table S4. Center of Gaussian fits, x_0 , for the experimentally measured mass spectra (x_0^{exp}) shown in Figures 4, S14-S18, and the corresponding theoretical mass distributions (x_0^{th}). The last column corresponds to the absolute error calculated as $x_0^{\text{exp}} - x_0^{\text{th}}$. The x_0^{th} of the K⁺ adduct shows a much larger shift with respect to x_0^{exp} than that of the Cl⁻ adduct.

	Molecular formula	z	Chemical Formula	Molecular weight*	x_0^{th}	x_0^{exp}	error
With NaCl	DNA ₂ ⁻ [Ag ₂₈] ¹⁶⁺	5-	C ₃₀₄ H ₃₈₆ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ [Ag ₂₈] ¹⁶⁺	12726.587 g/mol			
			C ₃₀₄ H ₃₇₀ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ Ag ₂₈	12710.460 g/mol	2541.079 ± 0.002	2541.144 ± 0.020	+ 0.065
			(C ₃₀₄ H ₃₆₅ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ Ag ₂₈) ⁵⁻	12705.421 g/mol			
		6-	C ₃₀₄ H ₃₈₆ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ [Ag ₂₈] ¹⁶⁺	12726.587 g/mol			
			C ₃₀₄ H ₃₇₀ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ Ag ₂₈	12710.460 g/mol	2117.395 ± 0.001	2117.468 ± 0.007	+ 0.073
			(C ₃₀₄ H ₃₆₄ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ Ag ₂₈) ⁶⁻	12704.413 g/mol			
	DNA ₂ ⁻ [Ag ₂₈ Cl] ¹⁵⁺	5-	C ₃₀₄ H ₃₈₆ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ [Ag ₂₈] ¹⁶⁺ Cl ⁻	12762.040 g/mol			
			C ₃₀₄ H ₃₇₁ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ Ag ₂₈ Cl	12746.921 g/mol	2548.364 ± 0.002	2548.354 ± 0.040	- 0.010
			(C ₃₀₄ H ₃₆₆ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ Ag ₂₈ Cl) ⁵⁻	12741.882 g/mol			
		6-	C ₃₀₄ H ₃₈₆ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ [Ag ₂₈] ¹⁶⁺ Cl ⁻	12762.040 g/mol			
			C ₃₀₄ H ₃₇₁ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ Ag ₂₈ Cl	12746.921 g/mol	2123.469 ± 0.002	2123.488 ± 0.050	+ 0.019
			(C ₃₀₄ H ₃₆₅ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ Ag ₂₈ Cl) ⁵⁻	12740.874 g/mol			
DNA ₂ ⁻ [Ag ₂₈ K] ¹⁷⁺	5-	C ₃₀₄ H ₃₈₆ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ [Ag ₂₈] ¹⁶⁺ K ⁺	12765.686 g/mol				
		C ₃₀₄ H ₃₆₉ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ Ag ₂₈ K	12748.551 g/mol	2548.695 ± 0.002	2548.354 ± 0.040	- 0.341	
		(C ₃₀₄ H ₃₆₄ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ Ag ₂₈ K) ⁵⁻	12743.511 g/mol				
	6-	C ₃₀₄ H ₃₈₆ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ [Ag ₂₈] ¹⁶⁺ K ⁺	12765.686 g/mol				
		C ₃₀₄ H ₃₆₉ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ Ag ₂₈ K	12748.551 g/mol	2123.740 ± 0.002	2123.488 ± 0.050	- 0.252	
		(C ₃₀₄ H ₃₆₃ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ Ag ₂₈ K) ⁵⁻	12742.503 g/mol				
Without NaCl	DNA ₂ ⁻ [Ag ₂₈ Cl] ¹⁵⁺	5-	C ₃₀₄ H ₃₈₆ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ [Ag ₂₈] ¹⁶⁺ Cl ⁻	12762.040 g/mol	2548.364 ± 0.002	2548.366 ± 0.020	+ 0.002
			C ₃₀₄ H ₃₇₁ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ Ag ₂₈ Cl	12746.921 g/mol			

DNA ₂ - [Ag ₂₈ K] ¹⁷⁺	6-	(C ₃₀₄ H ₃₆₆ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ Ag ₂₈ Cl) ⁵⁻	12741.882 g/mol				
		C ₃₀₄ H ₃₈₆ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ [Ag ₂₈] ¹⁶⁺ Cl ⁻	12762.040 g/mol				
		C ₃₀₄ H ₃₇₁ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ Ag ₂₈ Cl	12746.921 g/mol	2123.469 ± 0.002	2123.479 ± 0.010	+ 0.010	
	5-	(C ₃₀₄ H ₃₆₅ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ Ag ₂₈ Cl) ⁵⁻	12740.874 g/mol				
		C ₃₀₄ H ₃₈₆ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ [Ag ₂₈] ¹⁶⁺ K ⁺	12765.686 g/mol				
		C ₃₀₄ H ₃₆₉ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ Ag ₂₈ K	12748.551 g/mol	2548.695 ± 0.002	2548.366 ± 0.020	- 0.329	
		(C ₃₀₄ H ₃₆₄ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ Ag ₂₈ K) ⁵⁻	12743.511 g/mol				
		6-	C ₃₀₄ H ₃₈₆ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ [Ag ₂₈] ¹⁶⁺ K ⁺	12765.686 g/mol			
			C ₃₀₄ H ₃₆₉ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ Ag ₂₈ K	12748.551 g/mol	2123.740 ± 0.002	2123.479 ± 0.010	- 0.261
			(C ₃₀₄ H ₃₆₃ N ₁₂₈ O ₁₈₄ P ₃₀ Ag ₂₈ K) ⁵⁻	12742.503 g/mol			

* As determined by ChemDraw Pro 8.0.

Figure S14. Zoomed-in view of the molecular ion peak with $z=5^-$ charge state. The experimental isotopic distribution (blue) is reported with the corresponding Gaussian fit (lime) and the theoretical isotopic distribution (light green). The calculated average mass is m/z 2541.144. The sum formula is C₃₀₄H₃₇₀N₁₂₈O₁₈₄P₃₀Ag₂₈, which corresponds to a molecular mass of 12710.460 g/mol. The zoomed-in view of the molecular ion peak with $z=6^-$ charge state can be found in Figure 4B.

Figure S15. Mass spectrum of the 960-nm emissive DNA-AgNC in 50 mM NH₄OAc 5 minutes after the NaCl addition.

Figure S16. Zoomed-in views of ESI-MS spectra reported in Figures 4 and S15 for **A)** $z=6^-$ and **B)** $z=5^-$, highlighting the chlorine and sodium adducts of $\text{DNA}_2\text{-[Ag}_{28}\text{]}^{16+}$. See Figures S17 and S18 for the fit of the peaks.

Figure S17. Zoomed-in view of the mass spectrum reported in Figure S15. **A)** and **B)** Molecular ion peak with $z=6^-$ charge state. The experimental isotopic distribution is reported with the corresponding Gaussian fit (navy) and the theoretical isotopic distribution in light green for $\text{DNA}_2\text{-[Ag}_{28}\text{Cl}]^{15+}$ and purple for $\text{DNA}_2\text{-[Ag}_{28}\text{K}]^{17+}$. The experimental average mass is m/z 2123.479. **C)** and **D)** Molecular ion peak with $z=5^-$ charge state. The experimental isotopic distribution is reported with the corresponding Gaussian fit (navy) and the theoretical isotopic distribution in light green for $\text{DNA}_2\text{-[Ag}_{28}\text{Cl}]^{15+}$ and purple for $\text{DNA}_2\text{-[Ag}_{28}\text{K}]^{17+}$. The experimental average mass is m/z 2548.366. See Table S4 for the calculations.

Figure S18. Zoomed-in view of the mass spectrum reported in Figure 4. **A)** and **B)** Molecular ion peak with $z=6^-$ charge state. The experimental isotopic distribution is reported with the corresponding Gaussian fit (brown) and the theoretical isotopic distribution in light green for DNA₂-[Ag₂₈Cl]¹⁵⁺ and purple for DNA₂-[Ag₂₈K]¹⁷⁺. The experimental average mass is m/z 2123.488. **C)** and **D)** Molecular ion peak with $z=5^-$ charge state. The experimental isotopic distribution is reported with the corresponding Gaussian fit (brown) and the theoretical isotopic distribution in light green for DNA₂-[Ag₂₈Cl]¹⁵⁺ and purple for DNA₂-[Ag₂₈K]¹⁷⁺. The experimental average mass is m/z 2548.354. See Table S4 for the calculations.

6. Effect of NaCl addition on the absorption spectrum

To evaluate the stability of DNA₂-[Ag₂₈]¹⁶⁺ after the addition of NaCl, absorption spectra were measured before and after adding 1 μ L of a 154 mM NaCl solution to 3 mL of 0.43 μ M DNA₂-[Ag₂₈]¹⁶⁺. The stability was monitored up to 6 days after mixing.

Figure S19 shows that the addition of Cl⁻ induces an approximately 10-nm red-shift of the absorption maximum, accompanied by a minor 12% reduction in absorbance after six days, indicating an overall good stability of the DNA-AgNCs in the presence of NaCl.

Figure S19. Absorption spectra of DNA₂-[Ag₂₈]¹⁶⁺, purified only once via HPLC, before and at various time points after the addition of NaCl. DNA₂-[Ag₂₈]¹⁶⁺ were measured in 50 mM NH₄OAc at room temperature.

7. Energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectroscopy

The scanning electron microscopy and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy were performed with a JEOL JSM-7800F SEM and an Oxford Instruments X-Max 80 (model 51-XMX1178) using the AZtec 3.1 software to obtain spectra with a point & ID mode.

Figure S20. Same EDX spectra as those reported in Figure 5B, normalized to the Ag peak at 3.0 keV.

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